

ChoiRbot: New Toolkits for Cooperative Robotics in the ROS 2 Framework

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Abstract—In the last years, we have witnessed an increased interest in cooperative robotics applications. Notable examples include task allocation, model predictive control and formation control. Moreover, nowadays robots can be endowed with small yet powerful computing units, and can be connected among each others over a network. In this novel, *distributed set-up*, robots have to solve complex problems without a coordinating unit. By relying on their limited knowledge of the problem data, robots can exploit these computation and communication capabilities to execute these tasks, which often involve the solution of optimization problems.

Index Terms—Distributed Robot Systems; Software Architecture for Robotics; Optimization and Optimal Control

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last years, we have witnessed an increased interest in cooperative robotics applications. Notable examples include task allocation, model predictive control and formation control, see e.g. [1] and references therein. Moreover, nowadays robots can be endowed with small yet powerful computing units, and can be connected among each others over a network. In this novel, *distributed set-up*, robots have to solve complex problems without a coordinating unit. By relying on their limited knowledge of the problem data, robots can exploit these capabilities to execute these tasks, often involving the solution of optimization problems. The Robot Operating System (ROS) has been often used to implement robotics applications. The novel framework ROS 2 is extending ROS capabilities allowing for real-time control systems and large-scale networks of robots. However, state-of-art control architectures are typically optimized for very specific applications and are mainly focused on single-robot systems. Inter-robot communications are often simulated by all-to-all communications.

In this abstract we present CHAIRBOT [1], a ROS 2 framework for cooperative robotics. CHAIRBOT is written in Python and exploits all the novel functionalities of ROS 2. It allows users to easily run simulations and experiments on multi-robot systems with distributed optimization and control algorithms. In CHAIRBOT, each robot is viewed as a cyber-physical network agent with its own computing

unit that can communicate with neighboring agents according to a user-defined graph, possibly time-varying or unreliable. The toolbox does not require a central coordinating unit, thus allowing for the implementation of purely distributed algorithms. CHAIRBOT is fully integrated with DISROPT [2], a toolbox that allows to model and run customized distributed optimization algorithms. The toolbox also allows for the implementation of distributed feedback control laws that do not need optimization procedures but do require inter-robot communications. CHAIRBOT is available at <https://github.com/OPT4SMART/choirbot>.

II. CHAIRBOT ARCHITECTURE

The toolbox is structured in a layered architecture. Specifically, there is a *Team Guidance* layer and robot-specific layers, namely *RoboPlanning*, *RoboControl* and *RoboIntegration*. The Team Guidance layer is responsible for taking high-level decisions and for managing the robot lifecycle. The Team Guidance layer uses communication with neighbors in order to perform its tasks. The RoboPlanning and RoboControl layers are responsible for lower-level control actions as driven by the upper layer. The RoboIntegration layer can be used for simulation purposes to integrate the robot dynamics numerically. The main goal of CHAIRBOT is to ease the design and implementation of optimization-based distributed control schemes. Its central focus is on the Team Guidance layer, which provides boilerplate code for distributed computation, i.e. communication among computing robots over a graph, self-coordination and optimization algorithms.

In CHAIRBOT, robotic agents in the network run a ROS 2 process for each layer. To guarantee flexibility and code reusability, layers are implemented as Python classes, therefore they can be extended as needed for the specific application scenario. This gives the programmer a large degree of freedom and allows for the implementation of complex scenarios with only a few lines of code, as highlighted in the next section. A graphical illustration of the software architecture is in Figure 1.

A remarkable feature of CHAIRBOT is the possibility of performing almost interchangeably simulations or experiments on the same application scenario. Indeed, the toolbox is integrated with both the Gazebo software, a highly accurate robot simulator, and with motion capture systems such as Vicon, while for

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Fig. 1. CHAIRBOT architecture. Robots communicate with neighbors using the Team Guidance Layer. The Team Guidance class handles the communication with planning and control utilities, which are specific for each robot.

simpler scenarios one can also use the RoboIntegration layers associated with the RVIZ visualizer. The CHAIRBOT layers are totally agnostic of how the robot dynamics is actuated (whether in simulation or experimentally), thus making it easy for the user to switch from simulations to experiments.

III. BASIC USAGE WITH GAZEBO SIMULATIONS

Let us now illustrate how to implement a basic cooperative formation control scheme in CHAIRBOT. The goal is to drive robots to a formation in the $\{x, y\}$ plane. In order to achieve this formation in a distributed way, robots are assumed to communicate according to a fixed undirected graph $\mathcal{G} = (V, \mathcal{E})$, where $V = \{1, \dots, N\}$ is the set of vertices and $\mathcal{E} \subseteq V \times V$ is the graph edge set. We denote by \mathcal{N}_i the set of neighbors of robot i . The formation is specified with a set of desired inter-robot distances $d_{ij} \geq 0$ for all communicating pairs of robots $(i, j) \in \mathcal{E}$. In this scenario, at each time step the i -th robot communicates to neighboring robots a vector in \mathbb{R}^2 representing its position in the plane. Then, each robot applies the following distributed control law

$$\dot{x}_i(t) = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} (\|x_j(t) - x_i(t)\|^2 - d_{ij}^2)(x_j(t) - x_i(t)) \quad (1)$$

This scenario can be easily implemented in the described architecture described in by properly extending a Python class in the Team Guidance Layer. All is needed is to encode the control law (1) in a method named `evaluate_velocity`:

```
u = np.zeros(3)
for i, pos_i in neigh_data.items():
    error = pos_i - self.current_pose.position
    u += self.gain*(norm(error)**2 -
        self.weights[i]**2) * error
return u
```

To test the control law (1) on unicycle robots one can use an input conversion utility provided by CHAIRBOT, which recasts the single integrator input into linear and angular velocity using a diffeomorphism. The Gazebo software, a realistic robotic simulation platform, can be used to simulate the robot dynamics. The actual simulation can be easily run by leveraging the ROS 2 launch system. The user has to write a so-called launch file specifying the communication graph, the robot initial positions and the desired inter-robot distances.

The launch file can depend on external parameters such as, e.g., the total number of robots in the network. A simulation with e.g. $N = 6$ robots can be then run by simply executing:

```
ros2 launch choirbot_examples
    formationcontrol.launch.py -n 6
```

A video is available at <https://youtu.be/VIIIXpzPTfPU>.

A. Application to Multi-Robot Allocation Problems

In the following we present experimental results for teams of heterogeneous robots performing complex tasks leveraging the CHAIRBOT toolbox. Specifically, we show how CHAIRBOT allows for simulating allocation problems in teams of ground and aerial robots and to immediately translate these simulations into experiments with real robots. Indeed, thanks to its modular structure, CHAIRBOT makes it possible to switch from simulations to experiments in few, easy steps.

We employed the package to perform experiments for a cooperative pickup-and-delivery scenario in which robots have to pickup goods at given locations and delivery them in other locations. Robots have different load capabilities and they want to minimize the overall travel distance, while guaranteeing that all the goods are successfully delivered. This scenario can be formulated as a mixed-integer linear program with a large number of binary and continuous variables. We refer the reader to [3] for a detailed description of the problem and for the proposed distributed algorithm for its solution. We implemented the distributed scheme by coding the necessary steps into the Team Guidance layer and by using DISROPT [2] to encode the distributed optimization algorithm, which overall resulted in as low as 600 lines of code. A snapshot from an experiment with three Turtlebot 3 ground robots and two Crazyflie nano-quadrotors is given in Figure 2. A larger experiment with seven ground robots and two quadrotors is available at <https://youtu.be/NwqzIEBNIS4>. We also performed a simpler experiment for a distributed task assignment scenario. The mathematical description can be found in [1], while a video of the experiment is available at <https://youtu.be/uii1BJFGqMM>.

Fig. 2. Snapshot from an experiment. Red pins represent pickups, while blue pins represent deliveries. Paths travelled by robots are drawn as dashed lines.

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